

Effect of reaction time on the synthesis of InAs nanowire via solvothermal route

Chandni Devi, Sandeep Kumar*

* Central University of Rajasthan, NH-8 Bandarsindri, Dist. Ajmer-305817

sandeep.kumar@curaj.ac.in & Mob. No. 8290686644

Abstract

We have synthesized InAs nanowires (NWs) by using solvothermal method with the increase in reaction time from 30 min. to 2 hour. Structural analysis has been done by using FESEM (Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy). The nanowire has diameter in the range from 40-60 nm, whereas length up to 10 micro metre. Raman spectra was obtained in the spectrum range 170-280 cm^{-1} shows the redshift in the LO (Longitudinal Optical) and TO (Transverse Optical) mode, whereas blueshift in the SO (Surface Optical) phonon mode. Broadening in the TO and SO mode for InAs NWs with the increase in the reaction time $t = 30 \text{ min. to } 1 \text{ and } 2 \text{ Hour}$. The quantum confinement effect in NWs results downward frequency shift and broadening of TO and SO mode due to the relaxation of the $q = 0$ selection rule in the Raman scattering.